

An accurate determination of the refractive indices of water and glass by smartphone photography

Surajit Chakrabarti, Sanjoy Kumar Pal and Soumen Sarkar

Abstract

A smartphone can be used for many physics experiments by using the sensors built into the phone. Very precise measurements can be made using the camera of the smartphone. The sensor of the camera records the images of objects photographed in pixels which can be read off with micron level accuracy with the help of software available freely from the internet. The transverse magnification of the complex lens system of the camera can be shown to be the same as transverse magnification of a thin equivalent lens when it is placed at the first principal point of the lens system of the camera. The focal length of the equivalent lens can be determined accurately by an experiment though the position of the equivalent lens cannot be determined with that much accuracy. By taking two photographs of the same object from two different positions along the line of sight of the camera, the uncertainty of the position of the equivalent lens can be eliminated. The knowledge that an equivalent lens exists, allows us to find the distance and width of objects by analyzing their photographs. We do not have to really place the equivalent lens at the first focal position. By photographing the apparent position of an object immersed in water we have found the refractive index of water very accurately. We have also found the refractive index of glass in the shape of thin slides.

I. INTRODUCTION

A smart phone is a powerful instrument in the hands of a large section of people around the world. Students and teachers of physics in particular, can use it to perform many experiments, as is evident from different publications in educational journals from all over the world.¹ In a recent work² we have developed the basic method of determining the width and distance of an object by photographing it with a smartphone. It was implicitly assumed there that the complex lens system of the smartphone can be considered equivalent to a thin convex lens whose transverse magnification is the same as that produced by the camera when the equivalent lens is placed at the first principal point. Here in this work we have tried to explain the validity of this assumption.

The camera of a modern smartphone is a complex system of a number of lens elements which is packed within a few millimeters so that it can be housed within a smartphone of typical thickness of less than a centimeter. The method of determining the focal length of the equivalent lens of a smartphone camera experimentally has been discussed recently.³ One can find the transverse image size on the camera sensor in terms of pixel which are square shaped CMOS devices, using software available freely for both Windows and Apple operating systems (OS) from the internet. A relevant web search gives the length of a pixel in microns.⁴ By finding the magnification of an object one can find the focal length of the equivalent thin convex lens. This focal length can be found from a relevant web search also.⁵ However, being able to determine the focal length by performing an experiment and then checking it from website would be an invaluable and satisfying experience for the students. In another work⁶ the focal length has been determined by measuring the image size directly on the display of the smartphone. Discussions on pixels on the sensor of CCD cameras, can be found in journal paper^{7,8} and references therein.

In a recent paper⁹ the photograph on the display of the smartphone has been analyzed by the ImageJ software to find the focal length of the equivalent thin lens of the camera. However, this paper has raised some issues whether the single thin lens equation can be valid to describe the system.

In the present paper we have tried to answer this question by defining what is meant by an equivalent lens. We have first determined the focal lengths of the equivalent thin lenses of two cameras of two different smartphones. By photographing an object from two positions

separated by a distance, we have found the focal length of the equivalent thin lens with great accuracy which matches very well with the value found from the website.⁵ Once we know the focal length of the camera lens we can find the real depth of an object immersed in water. We can also find the apparent depth by taking three photographs. From these we can determine the refractive index.

In section II we have presented the theory of measurement of focal length of the camera and the method for determining the distance of an object by taking its photographs. In section III we have analyzed the compound system of two thin lenses separated by a distance. Here we have defined the effective focal length of a complex lens system and the principal planes. We have done this in a completely algebraic way without drawing any ray diagram as is usually done in text books. In Section IV we have introduced the concept of an equivalent lens. This helps us to understand why the replacement of the complex camera lens system by a thin lens placed at proper position is a valid argument. Then we have given experimental details and the results of our experiment. In the Appendix we have worked out some numerical problems taken from the text¹¹ to show that our algebraic formulation gives the same result as worked out in the text.

II. THEORY

When an image is formed by a convex lens, we have the relation

$$\frac{1}{v} - \frac{1}{u} = \frac{1}{f_c}. \quad (1)$$

Here u is the object distance and v is the image distance measured from the lens which is assumed to be thin. f_c is the focal length of the effective thin lens of the camera and is positive according to our sign convention. In the next section we will explain why this concept of a thin convex lens equivalent to the complex system of lenses of the camera is valid. When a real image is formed by a convex lens, object and image positions are on the opposite sides of the lens and the image is inverted. Transverse magnification produced by the lens is given by

$$m = \frac{v}{u} = \frac{I}{O} \quad (2)$$

where I and O denote the transverse sizes of the image and the object respectively and the magnification is negative. From the above two equations we have the algebraic relation

$$m = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{u}{f_c}} \quad (3)$$

Inverting this equation we get

$$f_c = \frac{u}{\frac{1}{m} - 1} \quad (4)$$

For an accurate determination of the focal length of the lens, we photograph the object from two positions of the camera shifted by a distance D along the line of sight of the lens. This measure cancels the uncertainty of the position of the equivalent thin lens inside the phone and D measures the actual displacement of the equivalent lens. If u_1 and u_2 are the distances of the object from two positions of the camera with transverse magnifications m_1

and m_2 respectively, we get

$$D = f_c \left(\frac{1}{m_2} - \frac{1}{m_1} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $D = u_2 - u_1$. In terms of the object and image sizes we can write $m_1 = \frac{I_1}{O}$ and $m_2 = \frac{I_2}{O}$ where O is the size of the object and I_1 and I_2 are the sizes of the images formed on the camera sensor. Since f_c is positive according to our convention we can write Eq.(5) as

$$f_c = \frac{|D|}{\left(\frac{1}{m_2} - \frac{1}{m_1} \right)} \quad (6)$$

In Eq.(5) the displacement D can be both towards or away from the object photographed. In Fig. 1, we show the lens configuration. The lens in the displaced position has been shown with dash marks. We determine f_c using Eq.(6) by determining I_1 , I_2 of an object of known width O and known displacement D of the smartphone.

Using Eq.(4) we get the distance of the object for which the magnification is known. For calculation of the magnitude of the object distance we write Eq.(4) as

$$|u| = f_c \left(\frac{1}{|m|} + 1 \right) \quad (7)$$

This equation allows us to find the apparent depth of an object placed beneath water or glass, very accurately by photographing the apparent image. From this we determine the refractive index of water or glass by the standard formula ^{10–15}

Real Depth

$$\mu = \frac{\text{Real Depth}}{\text{Apparent Depth}} \quad (8)$$

III. ANALYSIS OF A SYSTEM OF TWO COAXIAL THIN LENSES SEPARATED BY A DISTANCE

The smartphone camera is a complex system of lenses and the wide lens of our rear camera 1 consists of seven optical elements having a thickness 4.6mm.⁷ We first assume we have a system of two thin lenses of focal lengths f_1 and f_2 separated by a distance a . The equivalent lens is defined to be a thin lens of a definite focal length which when placed at a suitable position produces the same lateral magnification as that produced by the pair of lenses. The position of the final image produced by the pair is different from the position of the image formed by the effective lens. In this sense the equivalence is only partial. The focal length of the equivalent lens is called the equivalent focal length. The two lenses can be any type: both convex, both concave or one convex and the other concave. Suppose the object distance is u as measured from the first lens of focal length f_1 . The image distance is v' and this image serves as an object for the second lens of focal length f_2 . The final image distance is v measured from the second lens. Using the lens formula Eq. (1) we have

$$\frac{1}{v'} - \frac{1}{u} = \frac{1}{f_1} \quad (9)$$

From this we get

$$v' = \frac{uf_1}{u + f_1} \quad (10)$$

If the magnification produced by the first lens be m_1 then

$$\frac{1}{m_1} = \frac{u + f_1}{f_1} \quad (11)$$

The equation for refraction at the second lens is

$$\frac{1}{v} - \frac{1}{v' - a} = \frac{1}{f_2} \quad (12)$$

Eliminating v' in favour of u we get

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{1}{u} + \frac{u + f_1}{\dots} \quad (13)$$

$$v = f_2 \left(\frac{uf_1 - au - af_1}{u} \right)$$

If the magnification produced by the second lens be m_2 then

$$\frac{1}{m_2} = \frac{v^r - a}{v} \quad (14)$$

which from Eq. (12) can be written as

$$\frac{v^r - a}{v} = 1 + \frac{v^r - a}{f_2} \quad (15)$$

when we eliminate v^r from this equation in favour of u we arrive at the equation for the reciprocal of m_2 as

$$\frac{1}{m_2} = \frac{u(f_1 + f_2 - a) - af_1 + f_1f_2}{(u + f_1)f_2} \quad (16)$$

If the overall magnification be M then

$$\frac{1}{M} = u\left(\frac{1}{f_1} + \frac{1}{f_2} - \frac{a}{f_1f_2}\right) - \frac{a}{f_2} + 1 = \frac{u}{F} - \frac{a}{f_2} + 1 \quad (17)$$

where we define

$$\frac{1}{F} = \frac{1}{f_1} + \frac{1}{f_2} - \frac{a}{f_1f_2} \quad (18)$$

In this analysis all the equations are algebraic, that is, all the physical quantities can be positive or negative except a , the distance between the two lenses which is positive. Depending on the nature of the two lenses and their separation distance, all the distances and magnifications will follow with proper sign.

In Eq.(13) if u tends to infinity, the image distance becomes the focal length f^r of the system of two lenses as measured from the second lens. The focal length of the system becomes

$$f^r = \frac{f_2(f_1 - a)}{f_1 + f_2 - a} \quad (19)$$

This focal length is called the back focal length (b.f.l).^{11,12} Similarly when the object distance u is such that the image formed by the system tends to infinity, then the object distance is called the front focal length (f.f.l) as measured from the first lens. It is easy to check that

$$f = -\frac{f_1(f_2 - a)}{f_1 + f_2 - a} \quad (20)$$

where f is the f.f.l.

When the object distance is such that the overall magnification M of the system of lenses is unity then the plane perpendicular to the axis and passing through this point is called the first principal plane. It is easy to check that it is at a distance

$$H_1 = \frac{aF}{f_2} \quad (21)$$

from the first lens of focal length f_1 . The distance of the front focal point from the first principal point is $f - H_1$ and it is simple to show

$$f - H_1 = -F. \quad (22)$$

We can find the image point corresponding to H_1 using Eq.(13). It is found to be

$$H_2 = -\frac{aF}{f_1}. \quad (23)$$

This is also a unit magnification point and is called the second principal point. It can be shown easily that the distance of the back focal point f^r from H_2 is given by

$$f^r - H_2 = F. \quad (24)$$

So the effective focal length of the combination is F , however it is the focal distances when measured from the principal points.

When there is a number of coaxial lenses, we can find the position of the final image for a given object position extending this analysis to a number of lenses. Here also we will get two focal points. As the system of lenses has to be packed in a small space in a smartphone, camera manufacturers try to keep the back focal length f^r small. This focal length being small, any object at a reasonable distance from the camera will be effectively at infinity and so will be focussed on the sensor. Modern technology uses Optical Image Stability (OIS)¹³ and/or Sensor Shift Stability(SSS) techniques¹⁴ which are used to avoid blurr in image formation. These techniques essentially change the relative separation between the lens system and the sensor so that the iamage is always sharp on the sensor. Of course when the object to be photographed is very close to the camera, we cannot say the object is at infinity. Then we need ultra wide angled lens with different focal length to have sharp image on the sensor.

IV. EQUIVALENT LENS

Now suppose we remove the two lenses and place a single thin lens of focal length F at the first principal plane keeping the the object position same u from the original position of the first lens of focal length f_1 . So the object distance from the principal plane is $u - \frac{aF}{f_2}$. Now it is easy to show that the magnification produced by this thin lens is M , same as the

magnification of the original system of two lenses. This lens replacing the system is called the equivalent lens and its focal length the equivalent focal length. However, the image formed by this lens is not at the same position as that by the combination of the two lenses; they are laterally shifted.

This concept of an equivalent lens producing same magnification as a complex system is useful in analysing real situations as in the photograph produced by a smartphone. When we have a number of lenses coaxially placed one after another, we first find the equivalent focal length and its position. Then we combine this equivalent lens with the third one and find the equivalent focal length and its position. This equivalent lens has the magnification which is the product of the individual magnification of the three lenses. Proceeding like this till we reach the last lens in the camera, we finally get the equivalent focal length and position of the single equivalent lens with respect to the lens system of the camera. This equivalent focal length and its position are not known to us as we do not have any information of the lens system of the camera. However, we can determine the equivalent focal length by performing an experiment as we have discussed in the theory section. Only the position of the equivalent lens remains uncertain. By eliminating this uncertainty we have shown in the theory section how to determine the equivalent focal length accurately. When we measure the pixel length on the sensor we are getting the actual magnification; but we know this is going to be the magnification of the equivalent lens also. This knowledge gives us a powerful handle to use photographs to make very accurate measurements.

This analysis shows that an equivalent thin lens of a given focal length when placed at a suitable position can mimic the complex lens system of the smartphone as far as the transverse magnification is concerned. We are not going to place the hypothetical equivalent lens inside the camera. The knowledge that there exists an equivalent lens which can replace the whole system of lenses giving the same magnification when suitably placed, is enough to carry out analysis as we did in the theory section. We need not bother where the image is going to be formed by this equivalent lens and whether it can be focussed on the sensor.

V. EXPERIMENT

We have measured the refractive indices of water and glass with two Apple smartphones of model iPhone 12-Mini (which we call Camera 1) and model iPhone 12 Pro Max (Camera

2) respectively. In both the cameras we have used the standard wide lens option with " $\times 1$ " magnification.

We first determine the focal lengths of the two camera lenses. In Table 1 we present the data for camera 1. We take a ruler and stick it on a wall by a two sided glue tape. Then we photograph it focusing it properly from two distances with displacement D along the line of sight of the lens. u_1 and u_2 are the two distances of the camera from the ruler. When the image of the ruler is opened by the software Paint of Windows operating system, one can select a certain part of the image using the cursors of the software and can find the pixel difference between its two ends. We select 7cm of the ruler as our object width. After photographing we find the pixel difference on the sensor between two marks, say 10cm and 17cm marks as it is seen in the image plane. The pixel difference between these two marks has been presented as the pixel diff. in the table. From the internet one can find the pixel length for the particular model of the camera. 1 pixel was equal to $1.4 \mu\text{m}^4$ for our camera

1. From this we determine the width of the image corresponding to the object of width 7cm. From this and the displacement of the camera, we determine the focal length very accurately using Eq.(6). There is an uncertainty in the actual position of the lens inside the smartphone. We displace the smartphone by a known distance in order to eliminate this uncertainty. Here the displacement of the lens is the same as the displacement of the phone. In exactly the same way, we determine the focal length of the camera 2 for which 1 pixel is equal to $1.7 \mu\text{m}$.

To determine the refractive index of water we take an empty bucket and keep a small plastic ruler at the bottom. From a distance of about 10cm above the bucket we hold a smartphone by a stand and photograph the ruler. By analysing the photograph with the Paint software, we can easily find the image size in terms of pixels. Specifically we find the image width for two marks on the ruler separated by 4cm and find the magnification. Using Eq. (7) we get the distance of the ruler from the camera. Now putting some water in the bucket we, in the same way, find the distance of the apparent position of the object. Finally, we allow the ruler to float on the surface of water in the bucket and hence find the distance of the surface of water from the camera. All these three photographs are taken from the same position of the camera. From these three measurements we can determine the real depth as well as the apparent depth of the object. Once again the uncertainty in the position of the effective lens gets eliminated as we find the real and apparent depths by

subtracting two distances. We then determine the refractive index of water using Eq.(8).

In a similar way, we determine the refractive index of glass. We take three slides of the same glass material, of nominal thicknesses of 1,4,6 mm. We take a strip of a graph sheet and secure it on a flat and smooth wooden stool. We take a photograph of the graph sheet from a distance with a smartphone held by a stand. Then we put the glass slide, of a definite thickness, on the graph sheet. We take the photograph of the graph paper through the glass slide. Finally we remove the graph paper from the bottom of the glass slide and secure it on top of the glass. Then we take the third photograph of the graph sheet. Here also the camera position is kept fixed for the three photographs. From these photographs we determine the real depth which is nothing but the thickness of the glass slide. For each glass slide we determine the apparent depth inside the glass. From these we determine the refractive index of glass. Determination of the refractive index of water and glass by apparent depth method is old one.^{15–20} However, our method of taking photographs by a smartphone and finding real and apparent depth of an object may have some novelty.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The first row of Table 1 shows that our camera is at a distance of $u_1 = 30.0\text{cm}$ from the ruler. The camera was then shifted by 100.0cm to take the second photograph from a distance $u_2 = 130.0\text{cm}$. Magnifications in these two positions are determined and using Eq.(6) we determine the focal length of the lens. The process is repeated for 9 more times varying u_1 and D . The average focal length for camera 1 turns out to be $f_c = 0.423 \pm 0.001\text{cm}$. From the website⁵ we obtain the focal length of the lens as 0.42cm . Similarly we get the focal length of the second camera lens $f_c = 0.531 \pm 0.001\text{cm}$ whereas from the website we get it as 0.51 cm . We have adopted the same method for determining the focal length of camera 2 as in camera 1. We have not shown the data for this camera in tabular form.

The perfect matching between the focal length of the equivalent lens of camera 1 that we have measured and that given by the company for the first two significant digits, clearly shows that the thin equivalent lens approximation for the complex many element lens assembly of the smartphone is very good. Consistency and accuracy of our method gives one more significant digit than given in the company datasheet. Matching for camera 2 with

datasheet is within 4%.

In Tables 2 and 3 we discuss the measurement of the refractive index of water. In Table 2, u_1 denotes the distance of the ruler, placed at the bottom of the empty bucket, from the camera. The bucket is partially filled with water. The distance of the apparent position of the ruler, as seen by the camera, is u_3 . After taking two photographs we take up the ruler and float it carefully on the water. Once again it is photographed. Its distance from the camera is denoted by u_2 . Each row of Table 2 corresponds to the same row of table 3. Image sizes are determined from pixel readings and the transverse magnifications are obtained. Using Eq. (7) we calculate all distances u_1 , u_2 , and u_3 . From these we determine the real depth and the apparent depth of the ruler and hence the refractive index. We get the average value of the refractive index of water as $\mu = 1.327 \pm 0.004$. The refractive index of pure water with respect to air at 20°C can be found²¹ as 1.3312 at 656 nm. Our sample of water is not pure. The refractive index of water goes down with the rise in temperature.²² In our case the room temperature was 30°C. Assuming the presence of a small amount of dissolved material in our sample, we can claim that our result upto 4 significant figures matches that given in²¹ within experimental uncertainty.

We have determined the refractive index of glass using a second smartphone camera. In Tables 4 and 5 we show our data with the three glass slides. Here also each row of Table 4 corresponds to the corresponding row of table 5. For each slide we determine u_1, u_2, u_3 from the same position of the camera in the same way as described for water. For each slide we have taken photographs from 4 positions. As shown in Table 4 the average measured thicknesses of the slides turn out to be 1.2 mm, 4.0 mm and 6.0 mm. In Table 5 we show the average refractive index of glass slides which we determine to be 1.50 ± 0.01 .

VII. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have shown that taking photographs with a modern smartphone camera, we can find the distance of an object. The camera consists of a complex system of a number of lenses packed within a small length. The image is stored on powerful sensors whose pixel widths are available in relevant websites. This allows us to find the transverse magnification produced by this complex lens system accurately. A simple mathematics tells us that a thin lens of a given focal length can be placed suitably within the lens system such that it

gives the same transverse magnification as produced by the complex lens system. We can determine the focal length of this equivalent lens experimentally. The focal length and the magnification by the equivalent thin lens give the distance of the object from the thin lens though the position of the equivalent lens is little uncertain. However, if two objects are there along the line of sight of the camera, then the distance between the two objects can be found accurately eliminating the uncertainty of the position of the equivalent lens. Furthermore, we need not worry about where the image is going to be formed by this equivalent lens since we are not really replacing the complex lens system inside the camera.

Applying this formulation we have determined the real and apparent depths of an object immersed in water in a bucket by taking photograph of the object, looking vertically downwards. This gives us the refractive index of water accurate to three significant digits after decimal. This is an indirect verification of our formulation. Using the same technique we have determined the refractive index of glass in the shape of thin slides with minimum thickness 1.2 mm. The error in these measurements were slightly higher. We can determine the refractive index of any transparent liquid or a transparent solid with flat surfaces, very accurately, using this photographic method. The method is accurate and fast. As we discussed earlier² the method might be interesting for students to find the distance and height of far off objects just by taking two photographs. This method might prove useful for the process of surveying in future.

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TABLE I. Pixel data for the image sizes on the camera sensor from two distances:

Object size = 7cm

Smartphone :Apple iPhone 12-Mini ; 1 pixel=1.4 μ m

obs no.	u_1 cm	pixel diff. 1	l_1 cm	u_2 cm	pixel diff. 2	l_2 cm	f_c cm
1	30.0	712	0.0997	130.0	163	0.0228	0.422
2	40.0	537	0.0752	140.0	152	0.0213	0.424
3	30.0	712	0.0997	140.0	152	0.0213	0.426
4	40.0	537	0.0752	150.0	142	0.0199	0.425
5	50.0	427	0.0598	160.0	132	0.0185	0.421
6	40.0	537	0.0752	160.0	132	0.0185	0.421
7	50.0	427	0.0598	170.0	124	0.0174	0.421
8	30.0	712	0.0997	160.0	132	0.0185	0.422
9	40.0	537	0.0752	180.0	118	0.0165	0.423
10	30.0	712	0.0997	180.0	118	0.0165	0.424

TABLE II. Data for refractive index of water

u1=Distance to the bottom of the bucket from the camera

u2=Distance to the top of the water surface from the camera

Object size:4cm

Focal length of the lens $f_c=0.423$ cm

obs no.	pixel diff. 1	m1	u1 cm	pixel diff. 2	m2	u2 cm	Depth of water (u1-u2)cm
1	303	0.01060	40.33	333	0.01166	36.70	3.63
2	240	0.00840	50.78	272	0.00952	44.86	5.92
3	303	0.01060	40.33	373	0.01306	32.81	7.52
4	316	0.01106	38.67	401	0.01404	30.55	8.12
5	329	0.01152	37.14	449	0.01572	27.33	9.81
6	329	0.01152	37.14	601	0.02104	20.53	16.61
7	329	0.01152	37.14	772	0.02702	16.08	21.06
8	329	0.01152	37.14	1065	0.03728	11.77	25.37

TABLE III. Data for refractive index of water

u_3 = Distance of the virtual object from the camera

Object size :4cm

Focal length of the lens $f_c=0.423$ cm

obs	pixel	m3	u_3	Apparent depth	$\mu = \frac{u_1-u_2}{u_3-u_2}$	$\Delta \nu \mu$
no.	diff.	3	cm	(u_3-u_2)cm		
1	310	0.01085	39.41	2.71	1.339	
2	247	0.00864	49.38	4.52	1.310	
3	318	0.01113	38.43	5.62	1.338	
4	333	0.01166	36.70	6.15	1.320	1.327 ± 0.004
5	352	0.01232	34.76	7.43	1.320	
6	371	0.01298	33.01	12.48	1.331	
7	383	0.01340	31.99	15.91	1.324	
8	397	0.01390	30.85	19.08	1.330	

TABLE IV. Data for refractive index of glass

Object size=6cm

Smartphone:Apple iPhone 12 pro max

Pixel size= $1.7\mu m$; Focal length of the camera lens $f_c = 0.531 \pm 0.001\text{cm}$

u_1 =Distance of the graph sheet from the camera

u_2 =Distance to the top of glass slide

obs no.	Nominal thickness of slides mm	pixel diff. 1	m1	u1 cm	pixel diff. 2	m2	u2 cm	Thickness of glass slides(u_1-u_2) cm
1		1749	0.04956	11.24	1770	0.05015	11.12	0.12
2	1	1606	0.04550	12.20	1623	0.04598	12.08	0.12
3		1504	0.04261	12.99	1519	0.04304	12.87	0.12
4		1321	0.03743	14.72	1333	0.03777	14.59	0.13
5		1659	0.04700	11.83	1719	0.04870	11.43	0.40
6	4	1435	0.04066	13.59	1479	0.04190	13.20	0.39
7		1282	0.03632	15.15	1317	0.03732	14.76	0.39
8		1207	0.03420	16.06	1238	0.03508	15.67	0.39
9		1659	0.04700	11.83	1751	0.04961	11.23	0.60
10	6	1435	0.04066	13.59	1503	0.04258	13.00	0.59
11		1282	0.03632	15.15	1336	0.03785	14.56	0.59
12		1207	0.03420	16.06	1255	0.03556	15.46	0.60

TABLE V. Data for refractive index of glass

u_3 = Distance of the virtual object from the camera

Object size :6cm

	obs	pixel	m3	u_3	Apparent depth	$\mu = \frac{u_1 - u_2}{u_3 - u_2}$	$\Delta \nu \mu$
	no.	diff.	3	cm	($u_3 - u_2$)cm		
1	1756	0.04975	11.20	0.08	1.50		
2	1612	0.04567	12.16	0.08	1.50		
3	1509	0.04276	12.95	0.08	1.50		
4	1325	0.03754	14.68	0.09	1.44		
5	1679	0.04757	11.69	0.26	1.54		
6	1449	0.04106	13.46	0.26	1.50	1.50 ± 0.01	
7	1293	0.03664	15.02	0.26	1.50		
8	1217	0.03448	15.93	0.26	1.50		
9	1689	0.04786	11.62	0.39	1.54		
10	1457	0.04128	13.39	0.39	1.51		
11	1299	0.03680	14.96	0.40	1.48		
12	1223	0.03465	15.86	0.40	1.50		

Fig.1 Image formation at the two positions of the lens

Appendix A

Numerical Problem 1, Page 168¹¹

As an example we find the magnification of a compound lens system of two thin convex lenses.¹¹ Here the object is placed at 50.0cm from the first lens. The two lenses are separated by 20.0cm and having focal lengths 30.0 cm and 50.0 cm respectively.

$$\frac{1}{F} = 1/30.0 + 1/50.0 - 20.0/(30.0 \times 50.0) = 6.0/150.0\text{cm}^{-1}.$$

$$F = 25.0\text{cm}$$

$$1/M = -50.0/25.0 - 20.0/50.0 + 1 = -7/5$$

leading to

$$M = -0.714$$

This matches well with the result given in the text.

Numerical Problem 2, Page 246¹¹

We have a compound system of two thin lenses. $f_1 = -30.0\text{cm}$, $f_2 = 20.0\text{cm}$ and separation distance $a = 10.0\text{cm}$ We first calculate $1/F$ using Eq.(18)

$$1/F = 1/(-30.0) + 1/20.0 - 10.0/(-30.0 \times 20.0) = 1/30.0$$

$$F = 30.0\text{cm}$$

We then calculate the b.f.l using Eq.(19)

$$f^r = 20.0(-30.0 - 10.0)/(-30.0 + 20.0 - 10.0) = 40.0\text{cm}$$

Next we calculate f.f.l. using Eq.(20)

$$f = -(-30.0(20.0 - 10.0))/(-30.0 + 20.0 - 10.0) = -15.0\text{cm}$$

Using Eqs. (21), (23) we calculate the positions of first principal plane

$$H_1 = 15.0\text{cm}$$

and

$$H_2 = 10.0\text{cm}$$

They are all matching with the results in the text.